

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

Nasriddinova Mekhriniso Sharofiddin kizi,

Teacher of the Department of “Social and Humanitarian Sciences”,

Tashkent Institute of Management and Economics

mehrinisonasriddinova96@gmail.com

***Abstract:** inclusive education is one of the most important problems in the development of pedagogy and sociology today, as it is precisely this aspect that reflects the dynamics of societal development and its views on children with disabilities. The inclusive form of education is aimed at solving existing problems, it is recognized worldwide, and in recent years has become the most popular for people with disabilities. This article examines the development process of inclusive education, highlighting its main principles, models, and directions. The problems encountered in the implementation of this form of education are also presented. However, the main difficulty lies primarily in the lack of a unified approach to solving emerging difficulties, as inclusive education requires an individual approach. The relevance of the chosen topic is due to the need for quality education for disabled children to develop their skills and realize their potential.*

***Keywords:** inclusive education, disabled children, disability, socialization, general education schools, professional training of teachers.*

Introduction Inclusive education is the most pressing issue in the education system today. Considering this issue from the perspective of its historical development, schools for children with disabilities were first noted back in the 19th century. However, these were specialized educational institutions, and this stage of development is generally referred to as the pre-inclusive stage. Even later, in the 20th century, views on the problems of education for children with disabilities began to change, creating the first prerequisites for inclusive education. In the

1970s, the development of test technologies and their implementation in the educational system and pedagogical practice began.

History of inclusive education development in Uzbekistan

Uzbekistan is rapidly developing in all spheres and based on global trends. One of the modern and practical directions of national educational policy is the development of inclusive education. For this purpose, a number of measures are being implemented so that children with special needs can integrate into society and receive education. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On Measures for Further Improvement of the System of Education and Upbringing of Children with Special Educational Needs," adopted on October 13, 2020, serves as a vivid example of this.

This document defines a number of legal and organizational tasks that will allow the development of inclusive education in our country[3].

The Concept and "Roadmap" for the development of inclusive education for 2020-2025 have been approved. Target indicators for the development of education for children in need of special education until the corresponding period have been developed. The Concept will be implemented in two stages:

In 2020-2022: the regulatory framework in the field of inclusive education system will be improved; Training, retraining, and advanced training of qualified pedagogical personnel for the system; The material and technical base of institutions where inclusive education is introduced is strengthened, they are provided with special devices (lifting devices, ramps, handrails, etc.), necessary literature, methodological manuals, equipment and inventory for training in various professions; Modern information and communication technologies and innovative projects will be introduced into the sphere; By explaining the right of children with disabilities to education and the essence of inclusive education, a positive social environment is formed among the population;

In 2023-2025: gradual development of the inclusive education system, other

general secondary education of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

Teaching methods will be improved, and the principles of individualization will be gradually introduced into the educational process;

In the educational process, measures are taken aimed at the spiritual and moral education of students, their physical health and strong formation;

The number of specialized state educational institutions (schools and boarding schools) will be optimized based on their geographical location.

Principles of inclusive education. Regarding the direct methodological approaches to inclusive education, scholars highlight the unconditional positive aspects of this approach:

- developing friendly relationships with other children, each of whom has their own special abilities and skills;

- development of children's individual characteristics;

- inclusive education allows for the formation in children's minds of the need to accept children with different characteristics and thereby create a more favorable atmosphere of communication;

- communication with healthy children helps children with OVZ focus on their individuality and thereby consider themselves not as a person with deviations, but as a person with personal achievements;

- if we consider the inclusion process on a large scale, undoubtedly, this type of education contributes to the further socialization and inclusion of children with disabilities in professional orientation and effective adult life.

- all students receive equal opportunities and rights to education;

- with such an education system, children with disabilities are considered as important components of society as physically healthy children;

- students gain the opportunity to unlock their potential through the support of teachers with special training.

Inclusive education enhances the ability to educate children with disabilities

and creates a natural environment and develops a sense of unity among them:

- Students with disabilities are achieving progress;
- healthy competition is created among students;
- only this type of education can lead to changes in society and social attitudes

towards people with disabilities.

Models of inclusive education. Taking into account various individual needs, it is important to choose the right type of inclusive education. There are four models of inclusive education.

Complete Integration Model. Within this model, all students are taught at a general education institution in a standardized format, regardless of their health impairments. Full inclusion can be effective if a disabled child encounters a favorable learning environment and full socialization in the classroom. Otherwise, he will need additional training and psychological assistance and support from professionally trained teachers.

Partial Integration Model. In this model, children with special educational needs spend most of their time in general classrooms, but can also attend specialized classes or receive additional support outside the main classroom. This allows teachers to pay more attention to each student's individual needs.

Model of Special Classes. This model involves creating special classrooms for students with special educational needs. However, even in this case, they try to ensure the integration of such students into the general school life, for example, through the organization of general, sports, and cultural events.

Model of differentiated learning. In this model, learning is adapted to meet the needs of all students, including children with special educational needs. Here, various methods, materials, and approaches are used to make the educational process accessible and understandable to every student.

Problems of Inclusive Education. As in many other countries, the problems of inclusive education in Russia are inevitable. Despite some positive changes in

recent years, there are still obstacles hindering the full implementation of inclusive education in the country.

Firstly, one of the main problems is the teacher's lack of preparation for working with children with special needs. Many educators lack sufficient knowledge and skills to effectively teach children with various special educational needs. The shortage of specialists capable of working with such children is also a serious problem.

Secondly, the infrastructure of Uzbek schools does not always meet the needs of students with special needs. The lack of adapted premises, the lack of access to wheelchairs, and other physical barriers can hinder the full participation of all children in the educational process.

The third problem is related to society's attitude towards inclusive education. Some people still treat children with special needs with prejudice and stereotypes. This creates additional difficulties for inclusion, as such children may face interpersonal problems and negative attitudes from their peers and even teachers.

However, it should be noted that there are positive examples of successful implementation of inclusive education in Uzbekistan. Many schools and educators are actively working to create an inclusive environment and adapted programs for children with special needs. The government is also taking measures to increase the accessibility of inclusive education, however, large-scale efforts to address all the problems have not yet been undertaken.

Conclusion

In general, the problems of inclusive education in Uzbekistan are a complex and multifaceted issue that requires a comprehensive approach and joint efforts from educational institutions, teachers, the government, and society as a whole. It is important to continue the discussion, recognizing the real need to create equal and inclusive education for all children, regardless of their special needs. Based on all of the above, we can conclude that the development and actualization of

inclusive education is a reflection of society's readiness to adopt an inclusive culture, as well as the development of an equal rights policy towards children with disabilities.

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